

SUSTAINABLE ARCHITECTURE AS A VITAL PROCESS

Erdanov Panji Nuraliyevich

Lecturer, Termiz State University,
Faculty of Architecture and Construction

Annotation: This article discusses the factors influencing the development of architectural urban planning and how this ideology developed over time, what goals and objectives it sets for humanity. Sustainable architecture can be understood as a balance between newly discovered bioclimatic principles, local building traditions linked to the context, and original innovations that reduce resource consumption. The goal of sustainable architecture is not only to meet the "green" parameters and standards, but also to create, relying on them, an independent architecturally expressive form, thereby bridging the gap between two independent and irreconcilable discourses that have been unfolding in the architectural community in recent years.

Key words: architecture, environmental sustainability, "green architecture", energy saving, resource saving.

Introduction. Four components. Since the Age of Enlightenment, European civilization has developed in accordance with the philosophy of René Descartes. The Cartesian attitude to the world was scientific. The concept of "progress" appeared, which meant a constant improvement in the quality of life through the development of technology [1]. Nature was seen as a resource, the exploitation of which would bring material comfort to man. However, already at that distant time, voices were raised in defense of a more reasonable approach in relations with nature. Later, in the nineteenth century. Henry David Thoreau's lyrical hymn to nature, Walden, or

Life in the Woods, is often mistaken for the manifesto and start of the environmental movement [2, 3].

The architect Frank Lloyd Wright, influenced by the work of Henry Thoreau, developed the concept of "organic" architecture. He believed that the house is born as a living organism - from the meeting of the Spirit of the place and the Needs of the inhabitants. Wright in architecture relied on scientific, artistic and philosophical approaches, on the restoration of harmony between nature and man. This theme became the main one in the philosophy of Rudolf Steiner, which was still based on the views of Johann Wolfgang von Goethe. Anthroposophy has many followers from the end of the 19th century up to the present day. It influenced teachers and physicians, farmers and architects. At that time, several movements arose in opposition to the industrialization of construction and lifestyle. In the twentieth century, Alvar Aalto often called for respect for the "little man" and always fought against standardization in architecture, believing that this reduces its humanity.

The beginning of sustainable thinking is associated with the foundation after the Second World War of several international institutions. Thus, the International Institute for the Conservation of Nature, established in 1948, published as early as 1951 a study on the state of the environment on Earth. This is the first work in an effort to reconcile economics and ecology. The publication of the first report to the Club of Rome in 1972, *The Limits to Growth*, caused a minor revolution. Researchers led by Dennis Meadows have drawn public attention to the ruthless exploitation of natural resources, the waste of energy and water, and environmental pollution. They called for "zero growth" in the hope of slowing down this momentum.

In the same 1972, at the UN conference "Human Habitat", Barbara Ward and Rene Dubois proposed the motto "Think globally, act locally", which soon became widespread. *Factor Four*, a book by Amory and Hunter Lovins co-authored with Ernst Ulrich von Weizsäcker, founder of the Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy, talks about quadrupling productivity – doubling wealth

and halving resource use. In this report to the Club of Rome, the authors proposed 50 specific solutions for different areas of the economy, including many for the construction sector. For example, the concept of a passive house by Wolfgang Feist is just one of the proposals of this report. "Ecological footprint" became a term in the publication of two economists - Mathis Wackernagel from Switzerland and Canadian William Reese. The term intelligibly explained such a phenomenon as the consumption of biosphere resources by mankind. They calculated how much each person uses the biologically productive territory and water area necessary for the production of the resources he uses and the absorption and processing of his waste. Globally, we are now consuming renewable resources 50% faster than the Earth is capable of sustainably reproducing them. This and other information over the past 60 years has forced many people to change their behavior in everyday life and in the professional sphere in favor of a more environmentally sustainable [3, 4, 5, 8].

At present, it is difficult to find a conference, event or publication in the field of architecture or construction, where sustainable development would not be one of the main topics. Nevertheless, there are many definitions and explanations of this concept all over the world [6, 7, 9]. What has become a fundamental value for some, seems to others to be nothing more than irresponsible "green brainwashing" to promote their products. The term "sustainable architecture" can also have different interpretations. It may focus on energy use, building materials or social issues. Some associate the term with simple self-building technologies from wood, straw or clay, while others associate the term with high-tech construction and nanomaterials [10, 11].

Most often, buildings are perceived and developed as spatial objects, and their existence in time goes out of sight. They are perceived as static structures (real estate), but exist in this frozen, ideal state only in our imagination [12, 13]. In reality, the building is subject to changes in different periods of existence, it is less of an object and much more of a process.

This provision applies not only to interior design and engineering equipment. Architecture is constantly changing and deteriorating throughout its entire life cycle during operation, development, conservation and up to disposal. Architecture is a dynamic process and, as such, is neither immovable nor static [14].

Shaping tools. The goal of sustainable architecture is not only to meet the "green" parameters and standards, but also to create, relying on them, an independent architecturally expressive form, thereby bridging the gap between two independent and irreconcilable discourses that have been unfolding in the architectural community in recent years. On one side is a group that supports the importance of social value and, as a result, accountability of architecture. On the other hand, there is an influential group in architectural circles, which emphasizes only the cultural significance of architecture as its main and fundamental artistic value, as a "thing in itself". According to the famous Austrian architect Wolf D. Prix: "Sustainability does not recognize aesthetics and therefore it is not possible to create a common concept of sustainability and aesthetics. There is no working aesthetic of sustainability." The resolution of this conflict is possible through a holistic awareness of sustainability. Any attempt to build a sustainable building must focus on different goals: improved design and reduced resource consumption must work together with an innovative architectural concept and favorable location.

Conclusions. Social recognition, status and well-being are the key goals of both society and politics. Our consumer society has made us, first of all, not citizens, but consumers. The consumer believes that in addition to the obligation to consume, he has only rights. A citizen sees himself as an active participant in the life of society. In this role, he understands that he has both rights and responsibilities, and behaves accordingly. Eco-sustainable development can only be achieved with the participation of the entire civil society based on the concept of self-government. The willingness of consumers to reconsider their established standards of comfort is one of the most effective measures to reduce resource consumption. The transition to a society oriented towards sustainable development, to "being" does not imply a

change in the nature of behavior or cultural traditions, but further logical development, a transition to a new level of our human and social needs. In terms of the demands placed on the building, to increase energy and material efficiency, and to create a closed cycle of materials, this change makes the most sense in one thing - sufficiency. In other words, a close examination of established and traditional patterns of behavior and consumption calls for stopping the overspending of resources and energy, which is an ethical prerequisite for sustainable development.

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